

A Certain Evaluation Using Distance Concepts in Graphs

A Report

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G C BASVARAJU

Roll No:21SUPDR038

under the supervision of

Dr. Praveen B M

**DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, KARNATAKA, INDIA**

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I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Signature :

Name : G C BASAVARAJU
Roll No : 21SUPDR038

Place: MUKKA

Date:

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, – 574 146, Mangalore, Phone :0824-2477456
(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.
Web: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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Supervisor :

Dr. Praveen B.M
Director
Research and Innovation council
Srinivas University
Mukka, Mangalore-574146
Karnataka, India
Place : Mukka

Date : ___/___/_____

TITLE

**A Certain Evaluation Using Distance
Concepts in Graphs**

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Scholar Name

G C Basavaraju

DEDICATED TO
MY LOVING PARENTS
AND
TEACHERS

Synopsis

Different mathematicians have rediscovered graph theory many times while dealing with problems of their areas of work. These problems developed into different areas of graph theory like graph labelling, graph coloring, metric dimension, domination, graph decomposition, metro domination etc.

Let $G = G(V, E)$ be a graph. The order of G represented by $n = |V|$ and the size of G represented by $m = |E|$. The standard problem concerned the bridges of island named Königsberg city in Prussia, which is surrounded by Pregel river.

A connected graph G , the power graph G^n is the graph on the vertices of G with the relation that two vertices are adjacent in G^n whenever $d(u, v) \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, where $d(u, v)$ is the distance between the vertices u and v in G , if d is the diameter of G , then it turns out that G^d is a complete graph.

We recall that the minimum cardinality of a minimal subset D of $V(G)$ such that every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in D , is called domination number of the graph G and is denoted by $\gamma(G)$. And we recall that the metric dimension of graph G , denoted by $\beta(G)$, is defined as the cardinality of a minimal subset S of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v in G there exists w in S such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The set S is called the metric basis of G .

We define a vertex dominating set D of G called a metro dominating set whenever it also serves as a metric basis of G . The minimum cardinality of the metro dominating set is called metro domination number of G , is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

In this thesis we obtain results on the K- metro domination number for certain classes of graphs. This thesis consists of five chapters which give the details of the total work carried out by us.

It includes a brief introduction to the importance of the work done in the first chapter and developments made in the related field by us. And also which are needed for the subsequent characteristics and applications on graphs. It gives briefly metric dimension with definition, properties, previous results and applications, and also domination concepts using

examples and applications. It also provides some basic definitions and terminologies in metro domination. examples and applications. It also gives some basic definitions and terminologies in metro domination.

It includes literature survey in the second chapter . It also gives some past research work and terminology in metro domination

We discuss on the K- metro domination number of two cycles in the third chapter. We determine the lower bound for metro domination number of two cycles and on the order of the graph whose metro domination number is $k(\gamma_{\beta_k}(C_3XC_n))$. The results on powers of cycle are useful for the communication whenever each station amplifies the signals of the neighbouring station.

We determine the lower bound for K-metro domination number of open ladder graph in the fourth chapter. We determine the lower bounds on the order of the graph whose metro domination number is $k(\gamma_{\beta_k}(O(L_n)))$.

We conclude the results obtained by us during the last four years of research work with their importance and included the thesis with some open problems for future work in the eight chapter.

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List of Abbreviations

GCD	Greatest common divisor
LCM	Least common multiple
LUB	Least upper bound
GLB	Greatest lower bound
γ -set	Dominating set
MD-set	Metro dominating set
LD-set	Locating dominating set
$rn(G)$	Radio number of G
λ	Sum labeling
T	Tree
$osn(G)$	Outer sum number of graph G
$diam(G)$	Diameter of the graph G
$dim(G)$	Dimension of the graph G
$d(V)$	Degree of V
$d^-(V)$	In-degree of V
$d^+(V)$	Outer-degree of V
$ V $	Cardinality of V
$ E $	Cardinality of E
$\langle S \rangle$	Induced sub graph S
$P_m \times P_n$	Cross product of two paths
$C_m \times C_n$	Cross product of two cycle

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Science and Engineering

It is not the news that the development of science and technology makes it impossible to aware of all fields of knowledge, and specialization cannot be avoided in the scientific research where the rapid advances make it difficult even to follow the new results in the own specific discipline.

This unavoidable fact turns out to be a strong limitation in the development of science, since many achieved results in some discipline that could be useful in other fields of knowledge are in most cases unknown by scientists.

It is desirable that researchers know at least the existence of other field's advances. Although not being specialists on these other areas, they should know where to look for information in benefit of their own research.

Multi discipline teams and multi discipline areas are wards that now a days seems to be important in the scientific research. Indeed this is even more important if we focus on ancittae scientiae, i.e. sciences, which are used as tools in other sciences such as math's is with respect to engineering. Mathematicians are usually looking for new solutions. Dialogue of both areas is interesting for both communities.

Nevertheless dialogue is not always easy and requires from both mathematicians and engineers. The translation of a problem arising from Engineering to mathematical language requires a deep knowledge of the discipline in which a problem is contextualized. Setting up of assumptions and hypothesis of the model is always a compromise between realism and tractability. Finally the result given by the mathematical models must be validated with some experimental or simulation results.

In this thesis we deal with some problems of engineering which are useful in communication networks. We model the problem using the theory of graphs and solve it

using graph theory concepts.

1.2 Graph Theory Concepts

A graph $G = (V, E)$ is an ordered pair consisting of a nonempty set $V = V(G)$ of elements called vertices and a set $E = E(G)$ of unordered pairs of vertices called edges.

Two vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ are said to be adjacent if there is an edge $u, v \in E(G)$ joining them. The edge $u, v \in E(G)$ is said to be incident to vertices u and v . The degree of a vertex, denoted by $\deg(v)$ is the number of vertices in $V(G)$ adjacent to it. The minimum and maximum degrees of the graph δ and Δ respectively, are defined as the minimum and maximum over the degrees of all the vertices of the graph.

A uv -path is a sequence of distinct vertices $u = v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n = v$ such that v_{i-1} is adjacent to v_i for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, such a path is said to be of length n , A uv -path of length n is a cycle, denoted by C_n . Among all the uv -paths, the one having minimum length is called a shortest uv -path. A shortest uv -path is also called a Geodesic. A triangle formed in a graph G is often called a cycle of length 3, A graph is said to be connected if there is a path between every pair of vertices. If the graph is connected, the distance between every two vertices a and b , denoted by $d(a, b)$, is the length of shortest path joining a and b , and the diameter of the graph, denoted by $\text{diam}(G)$, is the maximum among the distances between all pairs of vertices of the graph.

The eccentricity of a vertex v of a graph G , denoted $e(G)$, is the maximum length of the shortest path from vertex v to a vertex of G . The minimum eccentricity among all the vertices of G is called the radius of G and denoted by $\gamma(G)$. The vertices u and v , which are at a distance equal to diameter of the length G are called antipodal vertices.

A vertex is joined to itself, forms a loop in G . Two or more edges join with the same vertices x and y called multiple edges. A graph having no loops or multiple edges is called a simple graph. The number of vertices in a graph G is called the order of G and

the number of edges in a graph G is called its size.

A vertex of degree one is called a pendant vertex and the edge incident with the pendant vertex is called the pendant edge. A vertex of degree zero is called an isolated vertex. A graph in which all the vertices are of equal degree is called a regular graph. A graph G is called r -regular graph if degree of its every vertex is r , a graph having no cycles is called an acyclic graph or a forest. A tree is a connected acyclic graph. A tree of order n is denoted by T_n .

Figure 1.2.1

A graph H is called a sub-graph of G if every vertex of H is a vertex in G and every edge of H is an edge of G . If H is a sub-graph of G and contains all the edges of G that join two vertices in $V(H)$ then H is said to be the induced sub-graph, denoted by $\langle H \rangle$. A maximal sub-graph of G is called its component. A complete graph is a simple graph with

an edge between every pair of vertices. A complete graph on n vertices is denoted by K_n . A graph is bipartite if its vertex set can be partitioned into two non-empty subsets v_1 and v_2 such that each edge of G has one end vertex in v_1 and other in v_2 . A complete bipartite is a bipartite graph in which each vertex of v_1 of order m is adjacent to all the vertices of v_2 of order n and is denoted by $K_{m,n}$. A graph $K_{1,n}$ is called a star.

Figure 1.2.2: Graph G and its complete graph

Two graphs G_1 and G_2 are said to be isomorphic if there exists a bijection f between their vertex sets such that two vertices are adjacent in G_1 if and only if their images under f are adjacent in G_2 .

If G is any graph and v is a vertex of G , then $G-v$ is a graph obtained from G by deleting the vertex v and all the edges incident with v and G . Similarly, if e is an edge of G , then $G-e$ is the graph obtained from G by just deleting the edge e in G .

A subset S of the vertex set V of a graph G , is called an independent set if no two vertices of S are adjacent in G .

Since a graph is a binary relationship within elements on a generic set, it is not

surprising that graphs appear, at least implicitly, in many different contexts of the scientific knowledge such as Sociology, Economy, or Engineering.

1.3 Graph Labeling

Most graph labelling methods trace their origin to one introduced by Rosa in 1967, or one given by Graham and Sloane in 1980.

Rosa called a function f a β -valuation of a graph G with q edges if f is an injection from the vertices of G to the set $\{0,1,2,\dots,q\}$ such that, when each edge xy is assigned the label $|f(x) - f(y)|$, the resulting edge labels are distinct. Despite the unabated procession of papers, there are few general results on graph labelling. Indeed, the papers focus on particular classes of graphs and methods and feature ad hoc arguments.

Labelled graphs serve as useful models for a broad range of applications such as: coding theory, X-ray crystallography, radar, astronomy, circuit design, communication network addressing and data base management.

1.4 Graph Theory Approach for Channel Assignment problem

Each network is a graph in which vertices are transmitters and any pair of vertices that may interfere is represented by an edge in a graph.

In 1980 'Hale' recast channel assignment problem in network engineering as graph labelling problem. In the original model the labels are integers and there is a specified set T of forbidden differences between the labels for adjacent vertices. In the quarter century since Hale's paper appeared there has been a flurry of activities on both the sides. The growth of wireless communication networks has spawned considerable activity in engineering literature on efficient channel assignment, while mathematicians have been fascinated by the problem of graph vertex labelling with conditions on their differences.

Graph coding is one such assignment. In proper coding we assign the codes to the vertices in such a way that the adjacent vertices receive the distinct codes.

In 1988, 'Roberts' described a channel assignment that had been proposed him by 'Tim

Lanfeair' at NATO. Integer channels are to be assigned to transmitters, and there are two levels of interference to be avoided, depending on the distance between the transmitters, due to spectral spreading.

1.5 Dominating Set

The domination problem was studied from the 1950s onwards, but the rate of research on domination significantly increased in the mid-1970s. In 1972 'Richard Karp' proved the 'Set cover problem' to be 'NP-complete'. This had immediate implications for the dominating set problem, as there are straight forward vertex to set and edge to non-disjoint-intersection bijections between the two problem to be 'NP-complete' as well.

Dominating sets are of practical interests in several areas. In 'wireless networking', dominating sets are used to find efficient roots within ad-hoc-mobile networks. They have also been used in document summarization, and in designing secure system for grids.

A subset of D of V such that every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in D , is called a dominating set and the minimum cardinality of a dominating set is called domination number of the graph G and is denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

For safeguard analysis of a facility, such as a fire protection, study of nuclear power plants, the facility can be modelled by a graph or network. For such applications, a vertex can represent a room, hallway, stairwell, courtyard, and etc. Each edge can connect two areas that are either physically adjacent or within sight or sound of each other. One primary function of a safeguard system is 'direction' of some object-perhaps detection of a fire, or detection of an intruder, such as saboteur. Suppose we have a detection device located at the vertex and the device can supply three outputs, such as

- (1) There is an object at the vertex
- (2) There is an object at one of the vertices adjacent to the vertex
- (3) There is no object at that vertex or any adjacent vertex.

It is necessary to determine a collection of vertices at which the detection device can be placed so that if there is an object at any vertex in the graph, it can be detected, and its

position uniquely identified.

In order to detect an object, which might be at any vertex in $V(G)$, it is necessary to have a dominating set. The additional problem uniquely identifying the location of the object requires a locating feature.

Example: 1.5.1: For the cycle C_8 , of figure 1.6.1, the subset $D = \{v_1, v_4, v_7\}$ of its vertex set is a minimal dominating set and hence $\gamma(C_8) = 3$.

Figure 1.5.1: Graph G and its minimum dominating set

1.6 Metric Dimension

F. Harary and R.A. Melter introduce the notion of metric dimension in 1976[15]. The metric dimension of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is the cardinality of a minimal subset S of V such that for each pair of vertices u, v of V there is a vertex w in S such that the length of shortest path from w to u is different from the length of shortest path from w to v .

The metric dimension of a graph G is also called as locating number of G and studied its dominating property independently by P.J. Slater in [67].

The co-ordinate associated with each node is based on the distance from the node to the landmarks, so as to pick just enough landmarks in such way that each node has a unique

tuple of co-ordinates.

A co-ordinate system on G is defined as follows, select a set M of ordered nodes as the landmarks. For each landmark, the co-ordinate of a node $v \in V$ in the G having the elements equal to the cardinality of the set M and i^{th} element of co-ordinate of v is equal to length of shortest path from i^{th} landmark to the vertex v in G .

Example 1.6.1. Consider the figure 1.6.1

Figure 1.6.1:(a) Graph G

Taking the vertices a and b of figure 1.6.1(a) as landmarks, the co-ordinates for the vertices are shown in figure 1.6.1(b).

Figure 1.6.1: (b) Graph G

However, by taking the vertices a and c of figure 1.6.1(a) as landmarks, the co-ordinates for the vertices in the figure 1.6.1(c).

Figure 1.6.1:(c) Graph G

Remark 1.6.2: For the above graph of figure 1.6.1(a), we obtained two different sets of landmarks namely $\{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$. Both of these consist of two elements. Further we observed that, there exists no singleton set of vertices satisfying the property that the associated coordinates of the vertices of the graph are all distinct with respect to the set. Thus the above sets are minimal with this property and such a minimum set of landmarks constitutes a metric basis. The cardinality of this metric basis is called metric dimension of the graph. On the other hand:

Definition 1.6.3: The metric dimension of a graph G , denoted $\beta(G)$, is defined as the cardinality of a minimal subset S of V having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v in G there exists a vertex w in S such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The coordinate of each vertex v of $V(G)$ with respect of each landmark u_i belong to S is defined as usual with i^{th} component of v as $d(v, u_i)$ for each i and is of dimension $\beta(G)$.

Remark 1.6.4: We obtain two distinct elements subsets $\{a, b\}$ and $\{a, c\}$ of $V(G)$ for the graph of figure 1.7.1 (a), both of which constitute a metric basis for G . However the second set is an internally stable set. Such sets often are more important to compute actual

metric dimension of our future graphs as it minimizes the number of landmarks by maximizing the possible assignments.

1.7 Locating domination number

P.J. Slater introduced the locating domination number in 1975 in his paper [67]. A dominating set D is called a locating dominating set or LD -set if for each pair of vertices u, v in $V - D$, $N_D(u) \neq N_D(v)$, where $N_D(u) = N(u) \cap D$.

The minimum cardinality in an LD -set of the graph G is called the locating domination number of G denoted by $\gamma_L(G)$.

Example 1.7.1: The set of darkened vertices of the graph G , of figure 1.7.1, serves as a minimal locating dominating set, so $\gamma_L(G) = 4$.

Figure 1.7.1:The graph G and its LD -set

1.8 Metro Domination Number

We define a metro dominating set, which can be served as a better alternating set for the locating dominating set as follows;

Metro Domination number introduced by B. Suryanarayana and Raghunath. P[6]. Finch and Ja-cobson[9] in 1985 introduced the concept of multiple domination.

Definition: A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of

vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$ is called the metro dominating set of D or simply an MD-set.

The minimum cardinality of a metro dominating set G is called metro domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

Example 1.8.1: Consider the graph of figure 1.9.1

Figure 1.8.1:The graph G and its MD-set

The set of darkened vertices of the graph G , of figure 1.9.1, serves as a minimal metro dominating set and hence $\gamma_\beta(G) = 3$.

1.9 Comparisons between Locating Dominating Set and Metro Dominating Set

For a graph G ;

- Both serves the same purpose of detection and unique identification of the objects in the network.
- Minimal metro dominating sets always contains fewer elements than that in a locating dominating set. For example the graph G of Figure 1.9.1(c), we observe that the metro domination number is 5 with a minimal MD-set shown in figure 1.9.1(c), but its locating domination number is 8 with a minimal LD-set of figure 1.9.1(b).
- Determination of metro domination number is harder than that of locating domination number.

- Locating domination number may or may not be defined (For example: for the graph C_3 , with a single element in $V - D$, we face a difficult for the comparison of neighborhoods as in the definition of LD-set), but the metro domination number always exists.
- Domination number $\leq$ Metro domination number $\leq$ locating domination number. For example consider figure 1.9.1(b) and figure 1.9.1(c) .in which it is shown that $\gamma(G) \neq \gamma_\beta(G) \neq \gamma_l(G)$.

Figure 1.9.1(a) The graph G

Figure 1.9.1: (b) The minimal LD-set of the graph G of figure 1.10.1

Figure 1.9.1: (c) The minimal MD-set of the graph G of figure 1.9.1

Figure 1.9.2:(a) The graph G

Figure 1.9.2: (b) The minimal γ -set of graph G of figure 1.9.2 shows that $\gamma(G) = 1$.

Figure 1.9.2: (c) A minimal MD-set as well as a minimal LD-set of the graph G of figure 1.9.2 Shows that $\gamma_L(G) = \gamma_\beta(G) = 2$.

$\gamma(G) = 2$

$\gamma_\beta(G) = 3$

$\gamma_L(G) = 4$

Figure 1.9.2: (d) The graph G with its various domination numbers

Chapter 2

Literature Survey

In 1976, Harary and Melter [3] introduce the notion of metric dimension. A set W is called a "resolving set" for G if the vertices of G have distinct representations with respect to W . The members of resolving set are called "landmarks". A resolving set containing a minimum number of vertices is called a "basis" for G . The number of vertices in a basis for G is its "Metric dimension" and denoted by $dim(G)$. If $dim(G) = k$, then G is called a k -Dimensional graph. Here we state the definition of Domination and its properties. The theory of Domination was introduced by Claude Berge in 1958. The inspiration for this concept was drawn from the classical problem of covering chessboard with minimum number of chess pieces. Although the mathematical study of dominating sets in graphs began around 1960. The subject has historical roots back in 1862 when De Jaenisch studied the problem of determining the minimum number of queens, which are necessary to cover (or dominate) an $n \times n$ chess board. As reported by W.W.Rouse ball in 1892, a chess enthusiast in the late 1800'S studied among others. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph, A set D of vertices in a graph G is called a dominating set of G , If every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D . The minimum number cardinality of a dominating set in G is called the domination number of G and denoted by $\gamma(G)$: A sub set D of $V(G)$ called a dominating set, if every vertex $V - D$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in D . The minimum cardinality of a dominating set is called the domination number of the graph G . The metric dimension of a graph G is the cardinality of minimal subset S of V such that for each pair of vertices u, v of V there is a vertex w in S such that the length of the shortest path from w to u is different from the length of a shortest path from w to v . The metric dimension of G is also called locating number of G . A dominating set D is called a locating dominating set or simply LD -set if for each pair of vertices u, v belongs to $V - D$, $ND(u) \neq ND(v)$, where, an LD -set of the graph G is called the locating domination number of G denoted by $L(G)$.

A subset D of $V(G)$ is called a dominating set (γ set) if every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in D . The minimum cardinality of a dominating set is called the domination number of the graph G and is denoted by $\gamma(G)$. F.Harary and R.A Melter [3], introduce the notion of metric dimension in 1976. The metric dimension of a graph $G(V, E)$ is the cardinality of a minimal subset S of D such that for each pair of vertices u, v of V there is a vertex w in S such that the length of the shortest path from w to u is different from the length of a shortest path from w to v .

Every graphs considered are simple, finite and connected. A graph $G(V, E)$ and $u, v \in V, d_G(u, v)$ denoted as distance between u and v . in G .

A subset $S \subseteq V$ is called resolving set if every pair of $u, v \in V$, there exist a vertex $w \in V$ such that the distance between the vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ in is represented as $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. A set of vertices $S \subseteq V(G)$ resolves G , then S is a resolving set S of G and its minimum cardinality is a metric basis of G , and its cardinality is the metric dimension of G , and represented by $\beta(G)$.

2.1 Applications

1. A moving point in a diagram might be situated by finding the separation from the point to the accumulation of sonar stations which have been appropriately situated in the chart. Here we are utilizing the Technique, adequately vast arrangement of marked vertices is a settling set for the chart space.
2. Given n coins, each one with different weights. Finding the weight of each coin with the least number of weightings, using the method in static optional the minimum number of weighings differs from $\dim(Q_n)$ by at most 1.

Let G be a graph with vertex set $W = V(G)$. If the vertices of graph have different representation with respect to set W then W is said to be a resolving set for the graph G . The elements of W are called landmarks.

A resolving set with the least number of vertices is known as “basis” and the number of vertices in a basis for G is called its metric dimension and denoted by $\dim(G)$ or $\beta(G)$. If $\dim(G) = k$, then G is said to be a k -dimensional graph.

The concept of multiple domination given by Finch and Jacobson [24] in the year 1985. A dominating set D in $V(G)$ is said to be k -dominating set in G , if each vertex of $V - D$ has minimum k neighbours in D . The cardinality of minimum k -dominating set is known as k -domination number $\gamma_k(G)$.

2.1.1 Some known results

1. Dominating sets in social network graphs.
2. A resource assignment problems on graphs.
3. Combinatorial optimization scheduling facility location.
4. Algorithm and theoretical outcomes on connectivity and domination.
5. Optimal domination graphs.
6. Domination in graphs and its application to social network theory.
7. On the computational complexity of codes in graphs.
8. A dynamic programming approach to the dominating set problem on k -tree.
9. A linear algorithm for the domination number of a tree.
10. On the restriction of some NP-complete graph problems to permutation graphs

2.1.2 Applications

Domination is a dynamic topic in graph theory, and has many applications to problems initiating from several fields such as engineering, business, sociology, economics, anthropology, psychology, linguistics, genetics, operation research, geography, computer sciences, architecture, biology, chemistry, theoretical physics, communication networks, distributed computing, web graph etc.

Suppose the small villages, in a remote part of the world like Alaska, Siberia, Himalayas to locate radio stations in some of these villages in the region. Since each radio station has a limited broadcasting, we must use several stations to reach all villages, but since radio stations are costly. We want to locate as few as possible, which can reach all other villages.

In the field of measuring, a typical job is to collect a topographic map of a tract of land by determining the locations and elevation of a selected set of control points. Guess we have communications links between cities to set up transmitting stations at some of the cities, so that every city can receive a message from at least one of the transmitting station. The result is again corresponds to a minimum dominating set.

2.1.3 Locating domination number

P.J. Slater introduced the locating domination number in 1975 in his paper [67]. A dominating set D is called a locating dominating set or LD -set if for each pair of vertices u, v in $V - D$, $N_D(u) \neq N_D(v)$, where $N_D(u) = N(u) \cap D$.

The minimum cardinality in an LD -set of the graph G is called the locating domination number of G denoted by $\gamma_L(G)$.

2.1.4 Example: Consider the graphs G

Figure 2.1.4: (a) Graph G and its minimal LD-set

Figure 2.1.4: (b) Graph G and its minimal LD-set

2.1.5 Metro Domination Number

Metro Domination number introduced by B. Suryanarayana and Raghunath. P[6]. Finch and Ja-cobson[24] in 1985 introduced the concept of multiple domination.

A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$ is called the metro dominating set of G or simply an MD -set.

The minimum cardinality of a metro dominating set G is called metro domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

2.1.6 Example: Consider the graphs G

Figure 2.1.6: (a) Graph G and its minimal MD-set

Figure 2.1.6: (b) Graph G and its minimal MD-set

2.1.7 Graphs Cartesian Product

Let G_1 and G_2 are two graphs. The Cartesian graph product $G = G_1 \square G_2$, some times called the graph product and some times denoted $G_1 X G_2$

Some graph Cartesian products C_n denotes a cycle graphs, K_n a complete graph, P_n a path graph and S_n a star graph.

Product	Result
$P_m \square P_n$	Grid graph
$P_m \square P_2$	Ladder graph
$P_l \square P_m \square P_n$	Grid graph
$C_m \square C_2$	Prism graph
$C_m \square C_n$	Torus grid graph
$S_{m+1} \square P_2$	Book graph
$\overline{K_m \square K_n}$	Complete graph
$K_2 \square K_n$	Crown graph

Vizing.V.G [13] was initiated by the domination number of cross products of graphs and also were intensively investigated in the past. The Cartesian product of two graphs g, h is a graph with vertex set $V(G) \times V(H)$ and $((g_1, h_1), (g_2, h_2)) \in E(G \times H)$ if and only if either $g_1 = g_2$ and $(h_1, h_2) \in E(H)$, or $(g_1, g_2) \in E(G)$ and $h_1 = h_2$.

Figure 2.1.7: (a) Graph $G (P_2 \square P_6)$

Figure 2.1.7: (b) Graph $G (C_3 \square C_6)$

2.1.8 Power graph

Let $G = (V, E)$ connected graph, K^{th} power is denoted by G^k . Whose vertex is same as that of G and two vertices (u, v) in G^k are adjacent K if and only if $d(u, v) \leq k$ in G .

2.1.9 Example: Consider the graphs G

Figure 2.1.9: (a) Graph G

Figure 2.1.9: (b) Graph G^2

2.2 Research gap

The minimum number of machines required to locate each and every vertex of the network is termed as the metric dimension and the set of all minimum possible number of landmarks constitute metric basis. The machines, where they placed at vertices of the network to know, their distances to sufficiently large set of landmarks and the positions of these machines on the net-work are uniquely determined. However there is neither the concept of direction nor that of visibility. Instead we shall assume that a Robot navigating on a Graph can sense the distance to a set of landmarks. Domination is an active subject in graph theory, and has numerous applications to problems originating from various diverse fields such as engineering, business, sociology, economics, an-, psychology, linguistics, genetics, operation research, geography, computer sciences, architecture, biology, chemistry, theoretical physics, communication networks, distributed computing, web graph etc Few to pen, Suppose that we have a collection of small villages in a remote part of the world. Example. Alaska, Siberia, Himalayas we would like to locate ratio stations in some of these villages in the region. Since each radio station has a limited broadcasting, we must use several stations to reach all villages, but since radio stations are costly. We want to locate as few as possible which can reach all other villages.

2.3 Objectives of research

The objectives of this study is as follows

1. To minimize the span of the LD-set.
2. To achieve the metro domination number of Cartesian product of two cycles.
3. To achieve the k-metro domination number of open ladder graph.

2.4 Methodology adopted

Calculations have been carried out using analytically and also numerical techniques like Quadratic formulae, variable separable method, mathematics techniques. etc, and analyzing the results by drawing the graphs using soft wares like mathematica, winedit 8, Texstudio and Origin.

Chapter 3

On the K-Metro Domination Number of Cartesian Product of $C_3 \square C_n$

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we determine some of known result on the K-metro domination number of Cartesian product of $C_m \square C_n$ ¹. All the graphs considered are simple, finite and connected. A graph $G = (V, E)$ and $u, v \in V$, $d_G(u, v)$ denoted as distance between u and v in G i.e. the length of a shortest u - v path.

In 1976, F.Harary and R.A.Melter[3] introduce the metric dimension of graph G . The vertex and edge sets of a graph G are represented as $V(G)$ and $E(G)$. The distance between vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ is represented as $d_G(v, w)$ or $d(v, w)$. A vertex $a \in V(G)$ resolves a pair of vertices $v, w \in V(G)$ if $d(v, a) \neq d(w, a)$. A set of vertices $S \subseteq V(G)$ resolves G , then S is a resolving set S of G and its minimum cardinality is a metric basis of G , and its cardinality is the metric dimension of G , denoted by $\beta(G)$. Let D be a dominating set, if every vertex is not in D is adjacent to at least one vertex in D . The minimum cardinality of a dominating set is called the domination number of the graph G , denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

The Cartesian product of two graphs G, H is a graph with vertex set $V(G) \times V(H)$ and $((g_1, h_1), (g_2, h_2)) \in E(G \square H)$ if and only if either $g_1 = g_2$ and $(h_1, h_2) \in E(H)$, or $(g_1, g_2) \in E(G)$ and $h_1 = h_2$.

Vizing.V.G [19] was initiated by the domination number of cross products of graphs and also were intensively investigated in the past (see [9],[13],[23]).

We define a metro dominating set and which can be served as a better alternating for the locating dominating set as, A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex a in D such that $d(u, a) \neq d(v, a)$ is called the metro dominating set of G . The minimum carnality of a metro dominating set of G is called metro domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

3.2 Some known results

1. If G is a connected claw free graph, then $\gamma(G) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$.
2. Let G be a graph. Then $\left\lceil \frac{n}{1 + \Delta(G)} \right\rceil \leq \gamma(G) \leq n - \Delta(G)$.
3. If $\text{diam}(G) \leq 3$, then $\gamma(G^2) \leq \delta(G)$.
4. Let G be a graph. Then $\gamma(G \square K)^2 = \gamma(G)$.
5. For every $n \geq 3$, $\gamma(C_n^2) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$.
6. For every $n \geq 1$, $\gamma(P_n^2) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$.
7. For every $m, n \geq 1$, $\gamma(P_m \square P_n)^2 \geq \left\lceil \frac{mn}{13} \right\rceil$.
8. For every $m, n \geq 3$, $\gamma(C_m \square C_n)^2 \geq \left\lceil \frac{mn}{13} \right\rceil$.

3.3 Main results

Theorem 3.3.1: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 10$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$.

Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 5 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{To Prove } \gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{6l-5} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 6)$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{6l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 4(\text{mod } 6)$$

We note that D is a 2-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

Theorem 3.3.2: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 12$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

$W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 7 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{To Prove } \gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{8l-7} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 8)$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{6l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 6(\text{mod } 8)$$

We note that D is a 3-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$$

Theorem 3.3.3: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 14$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

$W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 9 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{To Prove } \gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{10l-9} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1 \pmod{10}$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{10l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 8 \pmod{10}$$

We note that D is a 3-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$$

4.1 Generalization of K-MD set of $C_3 \times C_n$

Theorem 4.1: For all m, n $\gamma_{\beta_k}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{K+1} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 2K+6$

Proof: Consider $C_3 \times C_n$ as three canonical copies of C_n with vertices labelled $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of

the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least $2K + 6$ vertices including itself. The lower bound of $C_3 \times C_n$ of order $n = (2K + 6)l$ for some $l \geq 1$.

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{2(K+1)l-(2K+1)} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2(K+1))$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{2(K+1)l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 2K(\text{mod } 2(K+1))$$

We note that D is K -dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set

of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2] Thus $\gamma_{\beta_K}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{K+1} \right\rceil$

Chapter 4

On the K-Metro Domination Number of Open Ladder Graph

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we determine some of known result on the K-metro domination number of open ladder graph¹. Every graph considered here are simple, finite, undirected and connected. A graph $G = (V, E)$ and $u, v \in V$, $d_G(u, v)$ is denoted as distance between u and v in G .

A set $S \subseteq V$ is called resolving set if for every $u, v \in V$ there exist $w \in S$, such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The resolving set with minimum cardinality is called metric basis and its cardinality is called metric dimension and it is denoted by $\beta(G)$.

A set D of vertices in a graph G is called a dominating set of G , If every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D , The minimum number cardinality of a dominating set in G is called the domination number of G and denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$ is called the metro dominating set of G or simply MD -set. The minimum cardinality of a metro dominating set of G is called metro domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

Metro domination number introduced by B. Sooryanarayan and Raghunath.P[12]. A subset D of $V(G)$ is k -dominating in G if every vertex of $V - D$ has at least k neighbours in D . The cardinality of minimum k -dominating set is called k -domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_k(G)$. A dominating set D of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is called metro dominating set of G if for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$.

Corollary 4.1: For any integer n , $\beta[O(L_n)] = 2$

Corollary 4.2: For any integer n , $\gamma[O(L_n)] = \left\lfloor \frac{n+4}{2} \right\rfloor$

Corollary 4.3: For any integer $n \geq 8$, $\gamma_{\beta_2}[O(L_n)] = \left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \right\rfloor$

¹The results of this chapter are based on our paper titled "On the K-metro domination number of Open ladder graph" which will be published in "International Journal of Health Sciences" Vol:6(S9), 3766-3771,2022.

4.2 MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 4.2.1: For any integer n , $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 12$

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least five vertices including itself. Since metric dimension of an open ladder graph is 2, D itself serves as a metric set.

Thus $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \geq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$ (1)

To prove $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{12l-9} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 3 \pmod{12}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{12l-3} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 9 \pmod{12}$$

We note that D is 3- dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serve a metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 4.1.

Thus $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$ (2)

From (1) and (2)

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$$

Theorem 4.2.2: For any integer n , $\gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 16$

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least five vertices including itself. Since metric dimension of an open ladder graph is 2, D itself serves as a metric set.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \geq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

$$\text{To prove } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil$$

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{16l-12} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 4 \pmod{16}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{16l-4} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 12 \pmod{16}$$

We note that D is 4-dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serve a metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 4.1.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2)

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil$$

4.3 Generalization result

Theorem 4.3.1: For any integer n , $\gamma_{\beta_k}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{2k} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 4k$.

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths.

$W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D or at least at a distance 2 from at least one of the vertex D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominate at least $4k$ vertex including itself. The lower bound of $O(L_n)$, of order $n = 4kl$ for some $l \geq 1$.

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{4kl-3k} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv k \pmod{4k}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{4kl-k} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 3k \pmod{4k}$$

We note that D is also k -dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serve as metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 4.1.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_k}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{2k} \right\rceil, \quad n \geq 4k.$$

Ex: The 3-metro domination number of open ladder graph is 3

Figure (a): $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_{13})] = 3$

Ex: The 4-metro domination number of open ladder graph is 3

Figure (b): $\gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_{17})] = 3$

Chapter 5

Conclusion

P.J.Slater introduced the locating domination number in 1975 [67]. He determined locating domination number of power of path and power of cycles. And also he determined the locating domination number of Cartesian product of two paths and also he determined Cartesian product of cycles.

Determination of the locating domination number of a graph is equivalent to finding the least number of monitors that can do the contain task in a given graph or network. Metro dominating set served as better alternating set for the locating dominating set. Using this concepts we are found the results for Cartesian product of some graphs and power graphs which is absolutely finer than the locating domination number.

Further we are going to find metro domination number of Cartesian product of lexicographic graph. And also to find characterisation of metro domination number 2 and also to find characterisation of metro domination number 3. And also given one of the hardest open problem is;

Open Problem 5.1: Characterization of metro domination number 2 up to 8 vertices

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On the k-metro domination number of cartesian product of $C_3 \times C_n$

G C Basavaraju

Dept of Mathematics, Brindavan College of Engineering, Bangalore.

Email: basava.raju759@gmail.com

Praveen B M

Director, Research & Innovation Council, Srinia University, Mangalore.

Email: researchdirector@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Yogalashmi S

Dept of Mathematics, Atria institute of technology, Bangalore.

Email: yogalakshmis82@gmail.com

Vishukumar M

Dept of Mathematics, REVA University, Bangalore.

Email: vishukumarm@reva.edu.in

Abstract--A dominating set D of a graph $G=(V,E)$ is called metro dominating set G if for every pair of vertices u,v there exists a vertex w in D such that “ $d(u,w) \neq d(v,w)$.The K ”-metro domination number of Cartesian product of $C_3 \times C_n$ ($\gamma_{\beta_k}(C_3 \times C_n)$), is the order of smallest K -dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$ which resolves as a metric set. In this paper we determine K -metro domination number of Cartesian product of $C_3 \times C_n$.

Keywords---Distance matrix, metric dimension, Land mark, Dominating set, Metro dominating set, K-Dominating set.

1. Introduction

Let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph. A subset of vertices $D \subseteq V$ is called a dominating set (γ -set) if every vertex n adjacent to at least one vertex in D . The minimum cardinality of dominating set is called domination number of graph G and it is denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

“A subset $S \subseteq V$ is called resolving set if every pair of $u, v \in V$, there exist a vertex $w \in V$ such that the distance between vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ is represented as $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. A set of vertices $S \subseteq V(G)$ resolves G , then S is a resolving set S of G and its minimum cardinality is a metric basis of G , and its cardinality is called metric dimension of G and it is denoted by $\beta(G)$.”

“A subset D of $V(G)$ is K -dominating set in G if every vertex of $V - D$ has at least K neighbours in D . The cardinality of minimum K -dominating set is called K -domination number of G and it is denoted by $\gamma_K(G)$. A dominating set D of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is called metro dominating set G if for every pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The K -metro domination number of Cartesian product of graph G , is the order of smallest K -dominating set of graph G which resolves as a metric set.” Vizing V.G[5] was initiated by the domination number of cross products of graphs and also were intensively investigated in the past(See [9],[13],[23]).

”The Cartesian product of two graphs G, H is a graph with vertex set $V(G) \times V(H)$ and $((g_1, h_1), (g_2, h_2)) \in E(G \times H)$ if and only if either $g_1 = g_2$ and $(h_1, h_2) \in E(H)$ or $(g_1, g_2) \in E(G)$ and $(h = h_1 \cup h_2)$.”

2 Main Results

Theorem 2.1: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 10$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$.

Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 5 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil.$$

(1)

To Prove $\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{6l-5} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{6l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$$

We note that D is a 2-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

(2)

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_2}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

Theorem 2.2: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 12$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 7 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil.$$

(1)

To Prove $\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{8l-7} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{6l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 6 \pmod{8}$$

We note that D is a 3-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$$

(2)

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{4} \right\rceil$$

Theorem2.3: For all m, n , $\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 14$.

Proof: Let D be a dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$. Let $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i=1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least 9 vertices including itself. Since the metric dimension of $C_3 \times C_n$ is 3 if m or n is odd, and 4 otherwise [2]. D itself serves as a metric set.

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil.$$

(1)

To Prove $\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{10l-9} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1 \pmod{10}$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{10l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 8 \pmod{10}$$

We note that D is a 3-dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2].

Thus

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$$

(2)

From (1) and (2),

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}(C_3 \times C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{5} \right\rceil$$

3 Generalization of K-MD set of $C_3 \times C_n$

Theorem3.1: For all m, n $\gamma_{\beta_K}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{K+1} \right\rceil$, $n \geq 2K+6$

Proof: Consider $C_3 \times C_n$ as three canonical copies of C_n with vertices labelled $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$ & $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$ are the vertices of C_1, C_2 & C_3 respectively, such that for each $i, i=1, 2, \dots, n-1$. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$ is either adjacent to any of the vertex D or at least at distance two from at least one of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least $2K+6$ vertices

including itself. The lower bound of $C_3 \times C_n$ of order $n = (2K + 6)l$ for some $l \geq 1$

We define a set D as follows.

$$D_1 = \{u_{2(K+1)l-(2K+1)} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 1 \pmod{2(K+1)}$$

$$D_2 = \{w_{2(K+1)l-2} : l \geq 1\}, n \equiv 2K \pmod{2(K+1)}$$

We note that D is K -dominating set of $C_3 \times C_n$, and also D will serves as a

metric set of $C_3 \times C_n$ as in [2] Thus $\gamma_{\beta_K}(C_3 \times C_n) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{K+1} \right\rceil$

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K-Metro domination number of open ladder graph

G C Basavaraju

Dept of Mathematics, Brindavan College of Engineering, Bangalore.
Email: basava.raju759@gmail.com

Praveen B M

Director, Research & Innovation Council, Srinia University, Mangalore.
Email: researchdirector@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Lakshminarayana S

Dept of Mathematics, REVA University, Bangalore.
Email: narayan_sl@reva.edu.in

Vishukumar M

Dept of Mathematics, REVA University, Bangalore.
Email: vishukumarm@reva.edu.in

Abstract---A dominating set D of a graph $G = G(V, E)$ is called Metro dominating set of G . If for every pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The K-Metro domination number of open ladder graph $(\gamma_{\beta_k}(O(L_n)))$, is the order of smallest K-dominating set of $O(L_n)$ which serves as a metric set. In this paper we calculate K-Metro domination number of open ladder graph $(\gamma_{\beta_k}(O(L_n)))$.

Keywords---Dominating set, K-Dominating set, Domination number, Locating dominating set, Metric dimension, Metro dominating set.

1 Introduction

Every graph considered here are simple, finite, undirected and connected. A graph $G = (V, E)$ and $u, v \in V$, $d_G(u, v)$ is denoted as distance between u and v in G .

A set $S \subseteq V$ is called resolving set if for every $u, v \in V$ there exist $w \in S$, such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$. The resolving set with minimum cardinality is called metric basis and its cardinality is called metric dimension and it is denoted by $\beta(G)$.

A set D of vertices in a graph G is called a dominating set of G , If every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D , The minimum number cardinality of a dominating set in G is called the domination number of G and denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having the property that for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$ is called the metro dominating set of G or simply MD - set. The minimum cardinality of a metro dominating set of G is called metro domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$.

Metro domination number introduced by B.Sooranarayan and Raghunath.P[12]. A subset D of $V(G)$ is k -dominating in G if every vertex of $V - D$ has at least k neighbours in D . The cardinality of minimum k -dominating set is called k -domination number of G and is denoted by $\gamma_k(G)$. A dominating set D of a graph $G = (V, E)$ is called metro dominating set of G if for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$.

Corollary 1.1: For any integer n , $\beta[O(L_n)] = 2$

Corollary 1.2: For any integer n , $\gamma[O(L_n)] = \left\lfloor \frac{n+4}{2} \right\rfloor$

2 Main Results

Theorem 2.1: For any integer n ,

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil, n \geq 12$$

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$

is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least five vertices including itself. Since metric dimension of an open ladder graph is 2, D itself serves as a metric set.

Thus $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \geq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$ (1)

To prove $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{12l-9} : l \geq 1\} n \equiv 3 \pmod{12}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{12l-3} : l \geq 1\} n \equiv 9 \pmod{12}$$

We note that D is 3- dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serve a metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 1.1.

Thus $\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$ (2)

From (1) and (2)

$$\gamma_{\beta_3}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{6} \right\rceil$$

Example: The 3-metro domination number of slanting ladder graph 3.

Figure 1: $\gamma_{\beta_3}[S(L_{13})] = 3$

Theorem 2.1: “For any integer n,

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil, n \geq 16$$

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$

is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least five vertices including itself. Since metric dimension of an open ladder graph is 2, D itself serves as a metric set.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \geq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

$$\text{To prove } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil$$

We define a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{16l-12} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 4 \pmod{16}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{16l-4} : l \geq 1\} \quad n \equiv 12 \pmod{16}$$

We note that D is 4- dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serve a metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 1.1.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2)

$$\gamma_{\beta_4}[O(L_n)] = \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{8} \right\rceil$$

Example: The 4-metro domination number of slanting ladder graph is 3.

Figure 2: $\gamma_{\beta_4}[S(L_{17})] = 3$

Theorem 2.3: For any integer n ,

Proof: Let $G = O(L_n)$ be an open ladder graph on $2n$ vertices with $V(G) = \{u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(G) = \{u_i, u_{i+1}, v_i, v_{i+1} : 1 \leq i \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_i, v_i : 2 \leq i \leq n-1\}$ with for each i , $u_i v_i$ is the only edge between two paths. $W = V - D$, now each $v_i \in W$

is either adjacent to any of the vertex of D or a least at a distance 2 from at least one of the vertex D . Any vertex $v_k \in D$, will dominates at least $4k$ vertex including itself. The lower bound of $O(L_n)$, of order $n = 4kl$ for some $l \geq 1$.

We defines a set D as follows

$$D_1 = \{u_{4kl-3k} : l \geq 1\} n \equiv k \pmod{4k}$$

$$D_2 = \{v_{4kl-k} : l \geq 1\} n \equiv 3k \pmod{24k}$$

We note that D is also k -dominating set for $O(L_n)$ and also D will serves as metric set of $O(L_n)$ as in 1.3.

$$\text{Thus } \gamma_{\beta_k}[O(L_n)] \leq \left\lceil \frac{n+1}{2k} \right\rceil, \quad n \geq 4k.$$

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